

The International Bureau of Education's contribution to UNESCO's conceptualization of fairness and justice in education

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Abstract. Today's conception of justice and fairness in education, put forth by Sustainable Development Goal 4 as inclusion and equity, is the product of decades of intergovernmental cooperation. This paper explores how these accounts of justice and fairness in education have been shaped and integrated into the set of global education values put forth by the United Nations. It uses archives from one of the longest-lasting instances of intergovernmental cooperation in education, the International Conference on Public Education (1934-2008), to develop a lexical and semantic analysis of 75 years of international recommendations. It shows how the SDG 4 agenda inherited several features introduced as far back as the interwar period while also moving away from politically difficult understandings; progressively privileging relative over absolute justice and developing an imperfect procedural justice narrative to focus on achievement gap issues and leave aside dimensions such as pedagogy and lived experiences. Furthermore, it is shown that this historical trajectory cannot be detached from the institutional changes that the International Bureau of Education (IBE) had to face to ensure its survival. The progressive loss of substance and actionability of international recommendations parallels the bid for heightened political legitimacy at the expense of scientific authority, and eventually led to the sidelining of the IBE despite its foundational contributions to fostering justice and fairness in education.

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Introduction

Since the early years of intergovernmental cooperation in education, questions of justice and fairness in national education systems have been the object of discussions between countries. The contemporary international education agenda, Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG), dedicates an entire target, to “*eliminate gender disparities in education and ensure equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for the vulnerable, including persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples, and children in vulnerable situations*” (United Nations, 2015, p. 17). SDG 4.5, labelled the equity target, is the final product of years of intergovernmental cooperation, discussions and negotiations and together with the actual description of SDG 4 “*Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all*” (United Nations, 2015, p. 17) can be said to represent how justice and fairness in education, as global values, are thought about in the 21st century. Negotiations and agreements on global education values often take many years, if not decades, before becoming formalized in intergovernmental declarations, resolutions, or recommendations.

The chronotope of intergovernmental cooperation on justice and fairness in education is characterized by a multiplicity of loci, interacting with changes in actors’ influence and legitimacy, evolving geopolitical tensions and international architecture, the continuous evolution of educational knowledge, and the mutation of underlying societal values. There have, however, been a few defining moments that are known to have paradigmatically changed the definition and role of education, its relationship with justice and fairness, and eventually the development of national education systems. The creation of UNESCO and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights belong to this category. And there are some less visible threads, that slowly and progressively weave together to form the scientific, philosophical, and political foundations of these moments. The work of the International Bureau of Education (IBE), in part, belongs to this latter category.

How did the contemporary conceptualization of justice and fairness in education in international texts, as inclusion and equity, came to be? This paper proposes elements of response by looking into one of the longest-lasting instances of intergovernmental cooperation in education, the International Conference on Public Education (ICPE), later renamed the International Conference on Education (ICE), and hereafter simply named the Conference. Between 1934 and 2008, the IBE convened, organized, and informed the Conference, ensuring its preparation through the regular

implementation of surveys and statistical digests, monitored its follow-up, and, for many years, was perceived as a central knowledge holder and broker institution in education.

The notion of IBE as a center of intergovernmental cooperation in education is only officially established in 1946, but it is generally considered that even the preceding years qualify as intergovernmental cooperation (Hofstetter & Boss, 2022). Importantly, the ICPE is an instance of intergovernmental cooperation born out of intellectual cooperation, notably thanks to IBE's pioneering work in comparative education (Hofstetter & Schneuwly, 2024). And at least in the early years of the institution, its legitimacy hinged on the intellectual recognition of its staff, chief among them its longest-serving director, Jean Piaget.

The first Conference to endorse formal resolutions and recommendations took place in 1934, marking the beginning of a 75-years long series of official texts adopted at the end of each session. Recommendations, resolutions, and declarations by the Conference were the result of increasingly complex processes of intergovernmental cooperation in education. They often reflect months-long, sometimes years-long, developments including emergence and selection of an issue, preparatory work and documents, countries' debates and interventions, and final adoption¹. Despite the non-binding nature of most resolutions and recommendations, each word has been carefully weighed, scrutinized, and validated, and therefore, the vocabulary included in these resolutions can be said to reflect the highest level of international agreement reached at a given point in time on a given topic.

This paper focuses on the textual content of recommendations, resolutions, and declarations adopted after each Conference to discuss how justice and fairness in education have been incorporated into the realm of global education values in their current form. It identifies when and in what context the various elements that comprise today's conceptualization of justice and fairness in education emerged, stabilized, and became institutionalized, while other issues either disappeared or remained on the fringes. The next section introduces the data and method used, followed by an analysis of the current account of justice and fairness in education as understood

¹ See Brylinski (2022a) and Hofstetter & Schneuwly (2024) for detailed descriptions of these processes

within the international education agenda, and then by an analysis of the Conference's outcomes since 1934 to trace the emergence of these elements.

Approach and data

The study of intergovernmental cooperation in education requires to take a transnational history understanding, whereby the question of justice and fairness in education is considered to transcend national physical and intellectual boundaries (Iriye & Saunier, 2009) and constitutes a joint endeavor for all citizens, materialized early in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948). However, while it can be said that countries generally expressed support to the pursuit of these broad concepts, their inherently political nature requires to understand the duality of nation states endorsement of global resolutions or cooperation, between sincerity and strategy (Hathaway, 2007; Keohane, 1984; Wendt, 1987). Owing to this duality, official texts endorsed by International Organizations' (IOs) Member States often become very generic. While this typically favors consensus, it also considerably weakens the formative nature of resolutions by lessening their prescriptive content. So while the wording of international resolutions can be said to reflect the extent of intergovernmental consensus on a given issue at a given point in time, the informative content of texts might at times remain limited.

Education is one of these transnational issues where generic and neutral wording can become counterproductive, notably as it leads to multiple interpretations. There is evidence that this has allowed for unwarranted interpretations of global education values, such as equity in education (Montjouridès, 2022). Today's conception of justice and fairness in education, inclusion and equity in education, did not happen in a vacuum but is the product of decades of intergovernmental cooperation. Retracing the origins of SDG target 4.5 in officially endorsed resolutions, recommendations and declarations helps both to shed light on how far and sincere national governments and IOs are *vis-à-vis* their citizens' right and to illustrate changes in IOs' effectiveness, chief among them the United Nations, to secure clear, articulated and actionable global policy directions.

Influenced by Kuhn's understanding of historical science evolution, and in particular the idea of paradigm shifts and their likely incommensurability (Kuhn, 1963), this paper uses Bacchi's framework (2009), *What's the Problem Represented to be* (WPR), a foucauldian archaeology

methodological approach, to analyze lexical and semantic changes in international resolutions adopted at the Conference. It is used to describe how the issue of fairness and justice is represented over time, including some of the underlying assumptions, what is left aside, and the potential effects of such representation. The goal of this paper is to retrace historical changes that led to today's contemporary concept of inclusion and equity in education. It begins by proposing an interpretation of how equity in education is defined in Sustainable Development Goal 4, and specifically target 4.5. The paper then identifies when elements of this definition first emerged, how they evolved, and how they ultimately combined to form today's aspirations for educational justice and fairness.

In total, the outcomes of 45 Conference sessions, from its 3rd to its 48th, have been used to inform the analysis. Between 1934 and 2008, the Conference served as one of the main *fora* of intergovernmental cooperation in education. From its third session in 1934 to its last session in 2008, the ICE adopted a total of 7 resolutions (1934, 1935 and 1994), 91 recommendations (1936-1992, 1994, 1996, 2008), two declarations (1994, 1996) and two propositions of priority actions (2001, 2004). For the sake of simplicity these would hereafter be called Recommendations. Recommendations' numbering has been prolonged after 1992 and in the analysis, texts are cited using the following format "R XX, YYYY".

For the most recent periods, I also incorporate insights from international education monitoring sources—such as the Global Education Monitoring Reports and data from the UNESCO Institute for Statistics—alongside findings from an earlier bibliometric analysis, to examine how intergovernmental cooperation at the Conference aligns with trends in academic research and global education agendas. The analysis is divided into five different periods. The first period, 1934-1939, the interwar period, corresponds to IBE's time as an independent institute, moved by its desire to foster international intellectual cooperation and collaboration. The second period spans from 1946 to 1960, separating the post-war period from the post-colonial period, signaled by the UN Declaration on decolonization (United Nations, 1960). The third period spans 1961-1969 and corresponds to both the first UN Decade for Development and the final years of the IBE, before becoming the UNESCO International Bureau of Education in 1968. The fourth period spans from 1970 to 1990, the year the first international education agenda, the Education for All movement, was established. And finally, the fifth period, from 1991 to 2015, corresponds to the modern era

of global governance of education, where the international education community finds itself mobilized around a common, joint agenda for education. Thus, this last period connects the Conference's recommendations with contemporary forms of intergovernmental cooperation in education, such as the Sustainable Development Goals adopted in 2015.

The period 1934-1969 has been studied extensively by the ERHISE team at the University of Geneva and two chapters of the landmark volume by Hofstetter and Schneuwly, *The International Bureau of Education (1925-1968)*, "*The Ascent from the Individual to the Universal*" (2024) are of direct interest for the paper. Chapter 20 proposes an in-depth analysis of gender equality, and Chapter 21 discusses perspectives on social justice. These chapters, however, use documents outside of the final recommendations (in addition to looking at the content of the recommendations) and reveal conceptual, scientific, and political tensions behind the scenes. While building on these chapters, this paper focuses almost exclusively on the lexical and semantic analysis of the recommendations as the embodiment of a form of consensus in intergovernmental cooperation, taking a constructivist International Relations angle to analyze the texts. Expanding to later periods, more rarely analyzed in the literature, allows us to observe the concomitant evolution of educational ideas, governance changes, and intergovernmental agreements. Through the analysis of these recommendations, regularly distilled as reflecting, in theory, the concerted, negotiated, and agreed-upon, global view on education, the paper identifies potential paradigm shifts and traces precursors and discontinuities to contemporary elements of justice and fairness in education.

Intergovernmental cooperation in education² has historically happened in institutions such as UNESCO and the International Bureau of Education (IBE), the International Institute of Intellectual Cooperation (IICI), or the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (Brylinski, 2022b; Elfert & Ydesen, 2023; Hofstetter & Schneuwly, 2013, 2024). And while many scholars have rightly argued that global governance of education should go beyond

² Intergovernmental cooperation refers to formal and informal collaboration between states to address shared challenges, achieve mutual goals, or manage collective resources, while maintaining national sovereignty (Haas, 1964; Keohane, 1984). It can happen bilaterally or multilaterally (Paulo, 2014) and is typically facilitated by one or several International Organizations (Surdej, 2020).

state centrism (Elfert & Ydesen, 2023), it remains that those outputs of instances of intergovernmental cooperation, endorsed or adopted by national governments, such as the Sustainable Development Goals, constitute the bedrock of global actions and aspirations in education. It is only once sovereign states endorse these that they eventually gain access to legitimate global authority and can be invoked by all to justify actions and policies.

In this context, and as the global education landscape becomes more complex, it has also become exponentially more difficult to keep track of international “consensus” on global education values, priorities, and policy recommendations. The Conference provides an interesting reference point in this regard as it is probably the longest-lasting regular instance of intergovernmental cooperation in education from which outcomes sought global reach. This paper analyzes the entirety of the Conference’s outcomes between 1934, the year of the first resolution, and 2008, the year of the last Conference to date³.

Equity in education: how is it defined by the United Nations?

Today’s understanding of justice and fairness in education, as inclusion and equity in education, is embedded in SDG 4’s wording: “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all” (United Nations, 2015). While a global understanding remains to be reached, there usually is an agreement that they should be seen as processes rather than outcomes (UNESCO, 2020; Unterhalter, 2009). In practice, however, international monitoring has increasingly translated equity and inclusion into the management of achievement gaps. With the exception of the 2020 Global Education Monitoring Report on inclusion (2020), inclusive education remains conceptually elusive in global monitoring, while equitable education is operationalized as systematic group comparisons. Earlier analysis of international resolutions and monitoring reports by Montjouridès (2022) shows that discursive practices construct equity primarily as an *achievement-gap* issue.

³ In theory, the IBE may still have the mandate to organize the Conference (UNESCO, 2013) - but this has not happened in practice as the institution has been facing years of financial difficulties and perhaps even decades of an identity crisis.

Operationally, both the UN resolution and interpretive authorities for SDG 4 foreground specific groups defined by ascribed characteristics: gender, disability, indigenous populations, children in conflict, rurality, and poverty. Monitoring typically measure and contrasts gaps rather than interrogate systemic inequalities in access and pedagogy, recognition, and power. The most prominent gaps discussed; girls-boys, rural-urban, poorest-richest, largely mirror data availability, while other populations, such as children with disabilities and refugees, receive much uneven coverage. Thus, this over-reliance on quantitative monitoring, especially generic parity indices and visual group comparisons, has sidelined qualitative evidence and, with it, the difficult policy questions of lived experience, social justice, and structural barriers. Monitoring remains predominantly “summative” (judging outcomes) rather than “formative” (guiding improvement). The emphasis on comparative performance and accountability places the onus of “fairness” disproportionately on developing countries, while equity concerns in high-income systems (for example, access to and success in tertiary education) are comparatively neglected (Montjouridès, 2022).

Several consequential silences follow. Classroom practices and pedagogies, teaching methods, curricula, and learning environments are largely absent from the SDG 4 monitoring framework, which *de facto* functions as the principal discursive device translating global aspirations into operational categories. Fairness and justice thus become treated as results rather than processes embedded in everyday educational life. Although the SDG 4 framework, invokes equity as a human-rights concern, neither implementation nor monitoring systematically tracks social justice and inclusion. Power dynamics, cultural recognition, discrimination, and historically grounded accounts of injustice, such as the “education debt” (Ladson-Billings, 2006), are left aside.

Policy prescriptions consequently gravitate towards “better data” rather than transformative reform. This reinforces the institutionalization of the achievement-gap paradigm at the expense of holistic approaches, narrowing justice and fairness to what is measurable, so that what is measured becomes what matters. Inclusion and equity thereby shift the goalposts toward data work rather than the governance and pedagogical reforms required to confront entrenched inequities. Neutral terms such as “gaps” and “disparities” operate as discursive devices that circumvent sensitive but central issues, including historical injustice, structural power, and discrimination, and can deflect attention from governments’ responsibilities.

As Montjouridès (2022) argues, equity in education within the Education 2030 - SDG 4 agenda is principally conceived as a problem of imperfect procedural justice: the desired outcomes of institutional processes are presumed knowable and measurable, yet the policies, or the procedures to realize equity, are insufficiently specified to guarantee this outcome. Consequently, far more effort has flowed into measuring endpoints than into unpacking and assessing necessarily context-dependent reforms. In parallel, the rhetoric of “evidence-based policy” can displace IOs’ responsibility to understand policy processes onto others, while sustaining the appearance of actionable recommendation.

How did this consolidation occur? De facto, the contemporary global concept of equity in education has been delimited by SDG target 4.5, which prioritizes relative group comparisons and excludes minimum achievement (tracked under other targets). Although “inclusive and equitable education” can plausibly be read as requiring both absolute and relative standards (Montjourides, 2022; UNESCO Institute for Statistics et al., 2018), recent operational practice has contracted to performance-gap analysis, asking how well countries do rather than how fairly children are treated. This shift reflects a broader depoliticizing tendency in development discourse that favors targeted, technocratic interventions over ethical-political debate (Fukuda-Parr, 2019).

The next sections therefore examine whether, how, and when these elements appear in the Conference’s recommendations: the emergence of specific groups; the privileging of relative over absolute justice; the framing of equity as imperfect procedural justice; the confinement of fairness as a “developing-country” issue; and the place accorded to lived experience and pedagogy.

The interwar period (1934-1939): all educable should be educated

Between 1925 and 1939, the IBE was progressively establishing itself as one of the main *loci* of intellectual and later intergovernmental cooperation in education (Brylinski, 2022; Hofstetter and Boss, 2022; Hofstetter and Schneuwly, 2024). The Conference, became an important forum where education ideas, practices and policies were addressed and discussed annually with a transnational perspective and, from 1934, these discussions would conclude with the adoption of, first, resolutions (1934-1935), and, from 1936, recommendations, all numbered and building on previous ones upon needed.

Forty countries, three of which observers, and three international organizations were represented in 1934, a representation that will continue to grow before eventually encompassing all UNESCO Member States by 1970 and until its last session in 2008.

From the outset, concerns about what might be called absolute educational justice were explicit. The very first resolution (1934) urged a minimum number of years of schooling for all, recommending seven years of compulsory education (R 1, 1934). This early signal, that states must guarantee a minimum of educational provision, would echo in various ways throughout the remaining seven decades of the Conference. It also introduced “girls” as a specifically named group warranting attention. At the time, such group references were typically associated to skills deemed necessary to ascribed social roles, which in the case of girls was readiness to carry out household chores. The same rationale informed recommendations on forming “elites,” a core system function involving selection, tracking, and resource allocation to channel individuals where they could best “serve society” (R 2, 1934). From the beginning, meritocratic selection coexisted with a universalist ambition for public provision, mirroring debates within IBE circles (Hofstetter & Érhise, 2022).

The first ICPE cycles set a template that subsequent sessions extended: resolutions and recommendations articulated foundational minima for effective national systems—covering teachers (R 4 & 5, 1935; R 12, 1937; R 13, 1938), school construction (R 9, 1936), and textbooks (R 15, 1938)—and urged countries to reduce internal disparities. Recurrent attention fell on rural disadvantage (R 4, 1935; R 7–9, 1936) and on women and girls (R 2, 1934; R 8, 1936), two of the three enduring dichotomies that still organize contemporary equity debates. Notably, many texts translated principle into concrete measures: adapting school calendars and timetables in rural areas to seasonal labor cycles; establishing scholarships for poorer students.

A third priority group prominent in today’s justice/fairness agenda—children with disabilities—received a dedicated recommendation (R 7, 1936). Precursor to the idea of rights-based inclusive education, the text affirmed that such children are educable and should be integrated into the

education system under the same conditions as peers—albeit typically in specialized institutions at the time—and that additional resources (not least specialized teachers) were required.⁴

Concerns pertaining to justice and fairness had thus already started to emerge from the very first ICPE and, as extensively documented (Hofstetter & Érhise, 2022), reflected largely a conception of education that prevailed within IBE intellectual circles. Such conception was first preoccupied with ensuring the same minimum to all considered “educable” and second that this educability, although a feature of pretty much all children, still differed in degree from one individual to another and not all could pretend to any aspiration in society. Nevertheless, the idea that some groups required special care and funding and the notion of equality of treatment between regions and individuals were already in motion right from the beginning.

Equality of opportunity and the becoming of education as a Human Right (1946-1960)

The Conference resumed in 1946 as soon as the curtain closed on WWII. Against the backdrop of a nascent international architecture, the creation of the United Nations and its specialized education agency, UNESCO, recommendations integrated new foundational paradigms of justice and fairness, both in their rationales and in their policy prescriptions. The notion of “elites” disappeared, and educating for societal usefulness progressively became less prominent, with two notable exceptions that preserved role-based reasoning: women and children with intellectual disabilities. The idea of a right to be educated, enshrined in article 26 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, became infused as a justification for most recommendations made after 1948. This is also the result of the gradual rapprochement between the IBE and UNESCO, the latter seeking to establish legitimacy *vis-à-vis* its educational mandate and the former looking to cement itself within the new intergovernmental architecture (Hofstetter and Schneuwly, 2024). From 1947, invitations to the conference were issued jointly by UNESCO and the IBE (previously by the Swiss Federal Government), and recommendations began to reference ongoing international legal processes, notably the draft International Covenant on Human Rights, to justify free and

⁴ See Droux, Boss and Mole (2022) for a detailed account of the discussions that preceded the adoption of the resolution.

compulsory education and to urge states to prepare plans—within two years—to achieve it (R 32, 1951). UNESCO’s contribution to the Human Rights “architecture” was, in significant part, channeled through work prepared for and during the Conference (e.g., UNESCO’s 1950 Report to the Commission on Human Rights E_1752). The IBE leveraged this collaboration to strengthen the authority of its outputs; visibility increased when the recommendations were officially published in English for the first time in 1959.

The post-war period could be considered as the period during which the Conference’s recommendations were the most comprehensive *vis-à-vis* primary and secondary education curricula. Fourteen of thirty-two recommendations directly addressed subject-matter to be taught in primary or secondary education: hygiene, physical education, international awareness, writing, reading, geography, natural sciences, handcraft, mathematics, arts, alongside two dedicated to curriculum design (R 46, 1958; R 50, 1960). These recommendations did more than assert priorities: they canvassed pedagogical, administrative, and financial implications, reflecting a field led by pedagogists who were also attentive to system management. Yet not all subjects were framed as belonging to children’s right to education. Only reading (R 28, 1949) and mathematics (R 43, 1956) were explicitly presented as rights “for any human being, independently of their race, gender, condition, and activities” (R 28, 1949, p. 155).

The concept of equality of opportunity (“*égalité des chances*”) entered the realm of intergovernmental recommendations in 1946, with recommendation n°19 on equality of access to secondary education. It can be read as the first to expressly target the development of fair education systems (relative justice) where access must be granted solely based on educational achievement and not be hampered by any ascribed characteristic. It also introduced policies to target financial disadvantage and disparities in the learning environment are stressed as paramount, and this is the first recommendation that references the newly created UNESCO and what would later become a rights-based perspective on education, where every child must have the same opportunities for educational success. The earlier rationale of becoming a productive individual for the sake of society’s functioning has disappeared; only the idea of deserving individuals (meritocracy) remains, where a child’s educational achievement and competencies determine its options for continuing.

Across the period, recommendations insisted on equal access (R 21; R 32; R 33; R 34; R 40; R 47; R 51) and specified the means to achieve it. They defined minima: free primary education; foundational competences (R 28; R 43); and enabling provisions such as school canteens open to all to secure a minimal nutritional intake (R 33, 1951). There is also a general coherence and consistency within and across recommendations, thanks largely in part to the work of the IBE, whereby recommendations were systematically articulated with implementation pathways, prefiguring the forthcoming notion of education planning. Calls for compulsory education were accompanied by enablers: free textbooks, adapting to seasonality, the use of vernacular, remedial education, and alternative pathways to accommodate diverse learners. Minimum standards extended beyond as recommendation 28 (R28, 1949) stressed that both children and adults must be able to read.

Recommendation R 32 (1951) on compulsory education crystallised these shifts and introduced a new template structure: background and rationale; a call for studies (a precursor to today's evidence-based policy rhetoric); implementation details covering administration and teachers' roles; and, finally, a section on the role of IOs. Recommendation n°32 contains the first explicit mention of the right to education, citing both the 1948 Declaration on Human Rights, but also the draft International Covenant on Human Rights, that would only be adopted in 1966 as the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights.

Grounding recommendations in the right to education broadened the list of groups explicitly named in final texts. R 32 (1951) identified nomadic populations and speakers of languages with oral traditions as communities requiring tailored provision. Women, rural populations, and children with intellectual disabilities received dedicated recommendations on equal access (R 34, 1952; R 47, 1958; R 51, 1960). Yet, in the cases of women and of children with intellectual disabilities, a residual role-based logic persisted. Women must receive equality of access and educational treatment, yet accounting for psychological and physiological differences; they should be facilitated access to higher education, albeit in domains that are relevant for women; and they must be educated to convey the value of education to their children, to acquire aesthetic taste and eventually to play their “natural role” in the family and society (R 34, 1952). In the case of children with intellectual disabilities, although Recommendation n°51 invokes the right to education to call

for extending the duty of free and compulsory education to children with disabilities, the text also stresses that this would allow these children to become “useful” individuals.

Education financing featured centrally in recommendation 40 (1955) and intermittently throughout. Recommendations urged additional resources for groups whose rights were least fulfilled and acknowledged the opportunity costs borne by families when schooling replaced child labour. Fees, including for canteens and textbooks, must be aligned to households’ wealth when education is not free (R 19, 1946, R 32 & 33, 1951, R 40, 1955, R 47, 1958). Calling for the potential creation of an international education fund and posing the foundations of educational development assistance, recommendation n°40 stressed that claims of rights and equality of access should go hand in hand with commensurate funding, including financial incentives for teachers (R 47, 1958), if progress is expected towards universal access to primary education independently of race, social class, sex or religion. Many less developed countries struggled to finance these ambitions, and the period’s stress on financing and inequality helped justify the development of school censuses and education statistics. A recurrent triad: studies, plans, statistics, emerged (R 34, 1952).

Motivated by the need to preserve a difficultly achieved peace and to live up to the commitment made to erect its foundation in the minds of men, fueled by a newfound sense of humanity where it becomes an absolute and inalienable right to be guaranteed an education, the duty bearer of which being nation states, the post-war period laid out features that remain staples of contemporary justice and fairness discourses: rights, injustice, discrimination, equality, race, and class entered the intergovernmental lexicon. Citizens were increasingly treated as rights holders and governments have the duty to ensure this right⁵. This implied targeted support for groups whose rights remained unfulfilled, the bedrock of today’s equity agenda. At the same time, the right was mostly construed as a *right to access*. The Conference nonetheless also articulated absolute standards of educational justice: minimum decent clothing for school attendance; school meals; adequate buildings; enriched learning environments (e.g., addressing adult illiteracy, R 47, 1958; seeding small household libraries with textbooks, R 48, 1959); and core competences such as

⁵ For a richer and more detailed account of these issues, beyond the texts adopted by Member States, see Hofstetter and Schneuwly (2024).

reading and mathematics. Justice concerns extended to teachers: equal training and treatment for rural/urban and male/female teachers, and specialized preparation for those serving disadvantaged groups—so that all children could be taught by equally competent professionals.

By engaging with the legal obligations of States, ICPE's recommendations started to produce a perspective on justice and fairness that leaned towards perfect procedural justice, conveying the belief that establishing the right policies and processes would lead to equality of opportunity in education. By effectively establishing compulsory education, addressing women's access to education, or adequately developing education in rural areas, national education systems will develop into just and fair institutions. An understanding that became further cemented when, in 1960, UNESCO Member States adopted the first legally binding international instrument for education, the Convention Against Discrimination in Education (UNESCO, 1960a).

Technification coated in human rights, the emergence of educational planning (1961-1970)

The year 1960 was a pivotal year for the historical context surrounding intergovernmental cooperation in education. The “Year of Africa” brought 17 newly independent states into UNESCO, and the General Conference made education in Africa an organizational priority (UNESCO, 1960b). UNESCO would then go on to adopt “[n]umerous strongly worded resolutions” (Dutt, 2000, p. 246) throughout the 1960s. At the same General Conference, resolution n°1.221 invited all Member States to implement and follow-up on the ICPE recommendations. Education debates and discussions would welcome an increasing diversity of participants and views (Hofstetter & Schneuwly, 2024). Representation at the ICPE shifted rapidly: African sovereign states rose from 7 (9% of all represented States) in 1959 to 28 (30%) in 1963. Unsurprisingly, recommendations began to distinguish between concerns of more- and less-developed countries; the label developing countries (“*Pays en voie de développement*”) appears explicitly in recommendation n°52 (1961) and recurs thereafter. This decade, labelled the UN “Decade of Development” (Ajaegbo, 1986), was also IBE's last as an independent actor even as the Conference recommendations arguably reached peak international authority: UNESCO's ministerial mandates and funding expanded, while IBE's convening role gradually receded.

Throughout the 1960s, Article 26 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights was repeatedly cited (R 52, 1961, R 62 1967, R 66, 1970) or weaved into recommendations when possible, referencing the rights of parents and adults (R 53, 1961, R 58, 1965), children (R 55, 1962), teachers (R 61, 1966), or even justifying the importance of education for international understanding (R 64, 1968). This was strengthened by integrating other international declarations, conventions, and resolutions, progressively forming a dense, self-validating space for intergovernmental recommendations. This is illustrated by recommendation n°66 in 1970, which cites at least nine international instruments to justify reducing school dropout and improving system “effectiveness.”

Another interesting paradox appeared throughout the decade. As recommendations embraced a rapidly institutionalizing human-rights frame, justice and fairness were progressively subordinated to effectiveness and efficiency under the banner of ‘educational planning’. The shift presaged what Tomaševski later critiqued as transforming the urgency of a denied human right into a longer-term human development target (Klees & Thapliyal, 2007). So, even though concerns such as equality of conditions between children, treatment between teachers (R 52 & 53, 1961, R 57, 1963), the right to be educated by qualified teachers (R 55), striking inequalities in adult education levels (R 58, 1965), the need to eliminate racial and social discrimination (R 56, 1963) and continued attention to the situation of women and rural areas, were brought forth as rationales for action; one can perceive, cutting across all other recommendations, the concern for efficient spending and effective planning. ICPE’s recommendations started to be dominated by the lexical field and concepts belonging to the realm of what would become data-driven policies. Notions of rationalization, economic efficiency (R 54, 1962), and individuals’ usefulness to their society (R 56, 1963) permeated the narrative. In fact, very few recommendations were made on pedagogical matters after 1970. For example, although recommendation n°58 (1965) aims to tackle the issue of adult illiteracy, the text calls for studies to examine the extent of the issue, develop projections, and plan. There is no mention of trying to explore and understand systemic and qualitative reasons behind adult illiteracy. Similarly, by rationalizing what pedagogical research is (R 60, 1966) or by addressing school dropout primarily as economic wastage (R 66, 1970), recommendations made during this period did not necessarily contribute to foster justice and fairness in education but instead advanced its technicalization and demoted education from a right and an objective, of which the duty bearer are sovereign States, to a mean towards an economic end.

Enabling individual aspirations and the contribution to the international education architecture (1971-1990)

The 1970s are often presented as the decade during which global governance of education emerged (Mundy, 1999). In the background of the now-named International Conference on Education, the United Nations, unaware of the growing fatigue concerning development efforts, was promoting a second decade of development (Blair, 1983). Meanwhile, the World Bank sought ways to reinvigorate development by bringing back the “Marshall plan days” enthusiasm (Blair, 1983, p. 3). By the end of the 1960s and the early 1970s, UNESCO and the World Bank still belonged to common circles of influence. For example, a significant meeting took place during which George Woods (then President of the World Bank), René Maheu (UNESCO Director General) and William Clark (Overseas Development Institute Director) gathered over a weekend to discuss what would eventually become the Pearson Commission on International Development (1967); a model that would later inspire the Brandt Commission in 1977 (Blair, 1983).

At the same time, encouraged by the waves of independence, less developed countries and newly created ones were pushing for a New International Economic Order, more balanced and fairer, and the United Nations adopted a declaration establishing the new order

based on equity, sovereign equality, interdependence, common interest and cooperation among all States, irrespective of their economic and social systems which shall correct inequalities and redress existing injustices, make it possible to eliminate the widening gap between the developed and the developing countries and ensure steadily accelerating economic and social development and peace and justice for present and future generations. (United Nations, 1974, p. 1).

Among other features of the period that bear importance on the Conference resolutions stand two small changes: its new periodicity (every two years) and the full integration of the IBE into UNESCO, furthering its progressive sidelining. The IBE would typically be mentioned in cooperation and coordination with other UNESCO units or education institutions (e.g., R 67, 1971) and became largely confined to its pedagogical documentation and information programme, with the term ‘pedagogical’ even fading away by the end of the period. The inflationary use of international and regional declarations and recommendations to motivate those of the ICE continued, and the right to education’s architecture was brought in on every occasion. While there

was a substantive difference with the previous period, it was clear that the Conference's recommendations worked, at least in intention, towards establishing just and fair education systems.

In a similar fashion to the previous period, recommendation n°67 adopted in 1971 focused on mitigating inequalities, this time associated with children's social background ("milieu social"). By linking social background and likelihood of school success, this recommendation was the first to bring to the fore the notion of social justice and the fundamental link between human rights and inequality of educational opportunity. The recommendation explicitly discusses how social background affects both access and achievement in learning outcomes. It is also one of the rare attempts to include equality of opportunity as a determinant of education systems' effectiveness and as an element to take into consideration in educational planning. The recommendation took a comprehensive view of educational inequalities, it stressed the critical role of pre-primary education to level the playing field: made a first allusion to pre-primary education for all, highlighted the importance of orienting children, encouraged countries to engage with school zoning ("carte scolaire"), the French attempt at guaranteeing equal access to education, introduced the need for teachers to acquire further competencies to deal with classroom heterogeneity and address the needs of the most disadvantaged students. Basic minimum expenditures to be covered by governments were explicitly listed (school fees, textbooks and learning material, school meals, transport, and housing), with girls' education specifically highlighted as a priority for IOs, particularly for UNESCO.

This comprehensive attempt was followed by several recommendations that focused on individuals' aspirations, marking a departure from earlier discourses. The notion of individuals' aspirations appeared in recommendation n°68 (1973), which introduced the notion of lifelong learning following the reception of the Faure report, "Learning to be" (Faure et al., 1972), a report that substantially shaped the Conference's discussions that year. The report received both criticisms and praises and its major success was the introduction of lifelong learning as a key element of education systems and intergovernmental discussion (Elfert, 2019). Recommendation n°68 thus included lifelong learning as a mean towards greater equality of opportunity and called for a reform of secondary education that embeds this vision, notably by eliminating the underlying elitism behind tracking students, and eliminating any form of discrimination in students'

orientation. Adapting to an individual's aspirations also meant bridging across tracks and a better integration, as opposed to separation, of intellectual and manual activities in education. Improving the link between the right to education and the right to work was subsequently highlighted in recommendation n°73 (1981). Eliminating discrimination and referencing the 1960 Convention is a recurring feature of recommendations during the period; it is brought in most recommendations along with an expanding list of vulnerable groups. While in 1975 recommendation n°69 highlights race, color, sex, religion, political views and social status, additional categories became visible such as minorities, migrants and children in conflict-affected countries (R 72, 1979), ethnicity and refugees (R 74, 1984), as well as slum dwellers and cultural and linguistic minorities (R 77, 1990). Calling for reforming primary education to finally achieve free and compulsory primary schooling, and to ensure children's minimum development against all dimensions, physical, affective, social, intellectual and spiritual, recommendation n°74 asked for specific attention to the poorest, to girls and stressed the role of mother tongue, especially for migrants and refugees. By the same token, recommendation n°75 (1986) proposed to review textbooks and eliminate any racial prejudice and expression of hostility towards other populations.

Notably, and of significance for future developments, the period was also marked by three recommendations that laid the groundwork for a quantitative and comparative approach to educational issues. First, the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) developed by UNESCO was adopted, and recommendation n°70 (1975) was dedicated to promoting a wide adoption of the classification. Then the next two Conferences (1977 and 1979) focused on national and international information (R 71, 1977) and management (R 72, 1979) systems. Statistics and information became central elements to foster the right to education, and access to information a prominent issue for policy design, implementation, and follow-up, without which equal access to education, the elimination of discrimination, and the right to education could not be fulfilled. The IBE, together with other UNESCO units, was tasked to develop a world education information network as a central mechanism to support peace (R 71, 1977).

The period 1971-1990 ended with a number of well-known events. The push by developing countries for a New International Economic Order, which had even permeated the Conference recommendations (R 71, 1977), and notably supported by the Brandt Commission, was buried at the Cancun Economic Summit in 1981 by Reagan (Gilman, 2015), the Cold War ended, and in

education, the Education for All movement, and its framework for action were adopted in Jomtien in 1990. The World would be ushered into a series of international conferences on most and any development-related topic, and failure to integrate into the new global governance architecture might mean erosion of legitimacy and authority.

Against this backdrop and the multiplicity of instances of education-related intergovernmental cooperation, the ICE, the IBE, and UNESCO would be faced with strategic choices, compounded by the necessity to be effective and competent. In 1989, the ICE adopted its first and only recommendation dedicated to higher education (R 76, 1989), which is interestingly the first time the term “equity” appears in the Conference recommendations, in relation to access to post-secondary education. And while the recommendation stresses the importance of scholarships and of incentives to enroll girls in STEM fields, the end of the recommendation sends a somehow confusing signal by over-educationalizing development issues and laying out in a single sentence the role of postsecondary education to raise awareness of students on human rights violations, arms race, racism, environmental issues, poverty and hunger, illiteracy and all forms of exploitation.

Happening after Jomtien, the 1990 ICE could have been another opportunity to build on the global momentum. And the choice of illiteracy, one of the greatest and most striking educational injustices, could have appeared as very relevant. Recommendation n°77 anchored itself in Education for All and the Jomtien Framework for Action as well as in UNESCO’s Decade for Literacy, which started in 1987 and aimed to eliminate illiteracy by 2000. Foundational learning (reading, writing, and mathematics) was touted to steer education systems towards justice, equity, and priority was given to those countries that were left behind at the time. And the International Bureau of Education was tasked with the critical issue of following up.

More is less: reaching a vision for justice and fairness in education but failing to address the policies to reach it (1991-2015)

Since Jomtien (1990), global governance of education has been reconfigured around a common international agenda formally endorsed by governments and shaping national, regional, and international education strategies (Montjourides, 2022). The Education for All (EFA) conference at Jomtien set the frame; Dakar (World Education Forum, 2000) added a systematic monitoring mechanism (World Education Forum, 2000) and aligned with two education-related MDGs. The

same format persists under Education 2030 – SDG 4 (United Nations, 2015). This period also saw new bodies created to underpin the agenda: the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (1999) and the EFA Global Monitoring Report (2000), concretizing earlier calls for global statistical and information systems, for which the IBE had once been tasked to lead (R 71, 1977)..

In effect, this contemporary international architecture, where equity and inclusion, the contemporary conceptions of education justice and fairness, furthered the relegation of IBE and the Conference to secondary roles. Paradoxically, the last six Conferences produced recommendations that were, on paper, among the most expansive visions of justice and fairness, yet increasingly detached from implementable policy. For the first and only time, a recommendation targeted Ministries of Culture, broadening educational justice to the integration of education, culture, and development (R 78, 1992). The recommendation proposed a reference framework and nineteen guiding principles to foster a better integration of cultural issues into education systems. These ranged from multiculturalism, to mother tongue education, the development of ethical and civic values and media education. They, however, remained at the level of generic principles and read as global aspirations more than actual policy recommendations. What would typically take the span of one full recommendation in previous Conferences was reduced to one generic paragraph establishing values and visions more than actionable policies.

Two excerpts illustrate this evolution. Paragraph 12 of recommendation 78 on curriculum reads: “12. *The cultural and intercultural dimension in curricula: It is essential to recognise the role of culture as the foundation on which the content of education is built. The syllabuses of various disciplines, including scientific and technological ones, should therefore be prepared with the participation of specialists in cultural and educational specialists as well as anthropologists, sociologists, psychologists and others.*” (R 78, 1992, p. 26). Paragraph 28 on teachers states: “28. *The role and training of teachers: In the promotion of the contribution of education to cultural development, the teacher plays the most vital and unique role. In this context, a true sense of commitment on the part of the teacher is very necessary. Thus, his or her services should be recognized and appreciated by the community.*” (R 78, 1992, p. 26). The normative ambition is clear; but the policy “how” is thin.

In effect, evolution of teacher-focused recommendations underscores the trend. Earlier texts were level-specific and operational: in 1935, separate recommendations for primary and secondary

defined free teacher education and the theoretical, moral, and practical content of training (R 4 and R 5, 1935); in 1953 and 1954, primary and secondary were again addressed distinctly (R 36, 1953, R 38, 1954). By 1975 and especially 1996, level-specificity disappeared; “teacher” became a generic category governed by universal principles. Justice and fairness language broadened accordingly. Recommendation 82 (1996) calls for “*grant[ing] particular attention to the development among teachers of attitudes encouraging successful learning among their pupils, particularly those pupils from disadvantaged groups (physically, socio-economically and geographically) and from cultures different from the dominant one*” and for “*aim[ing], both quantitatively and qualitatively, at training teachers able to satisfy the needs of different ethnic and cultural groups, of those with special education needs and from remote regions, people living in extreme poverty or those affected by conflict.*” (R 82, 1996). A clear contrast with the earlier implementable minima (e.g., free training, equivalence across levels, mobility standards) recommended by the Conference.

Thus despite an all-time high participation during the period, with more than 130 countries represented and the presence of 80 Ministers of Education or more, it would appear that the Conference, the IBE and to a lesser extent UNESCO, succumbed to a progressive loss of policy substance in exchange of broader, generic yet ambitious, political statements. They reaffirmed the wide-ranging and multidimensional nature of education, its instrumental role in fostering peace, other human rights, and highlighted equity and inclusion as global objectives of education systems, foreshadowing Sustainable Development Goal 4. The last two declarations, in 2004 and 2008, foregrounded the elimination of gender inequalities, social exclusion, and poverty-related inequalities as priorities to tackle for achieving Education for All and the Millennium Development Goals, and stressed the need for multi-pronged strategies to address the issue of overlapping disadvantages. *Social inclusion* is introduced for the first time as a key educational challenge in 2004 (R 101, 2004) and *Inclusive Education* will conclude 75 years of Conferences as the last theme addressed in this forum. Despite establishing an extensive catalogue of normative principles for education systems, later conferences—particularly the 48th session—largely confined themselves to generic, non-prescriptive formulations, at times verging on the platitudinous.. For instance, 48th session’s Public Policies section calls for “*Pursu[ing] education in the public interest and strengthen[ing] the government’s capacity to orientate, promote and follow up on the development of equitable education of high quality in close partnership with civil*

society and the private sector” and “Develop[ing] policies that provide educational support for different categories of learners in order to facilitate their development in regular schools.” (R 92, 2008, p. 19). This contrasts dramatically with the inaugural intent set by Piaget to make “[t]he resolutions from [the] Conference [...] a catalogue of potential solutions”⁶ (IBE, 1934, p. 30) to the diversity and idiosyncrasy of educational challenges faced by sovereign countries.

Recommendations became declarations, the Conference sought to blend in with contemporary political and conceptual innovations, engaging in 1994 with the World Plan of Action on Education for Human Rights and Democracy co-led by UNESCO and adopted in Montreal in 1993, integrating in 2001 the notion of “learning to live together” introduced by the Delors report and the Dakar Framework for action, recalling the importance of teachers 30 years after the UNESCO/ILO recommendation on teachers adopted in 1966, or looking at the issue of education quality for youth to support the Millennium Development Goals and the Education for All movement. But what the Conference won temporarily, international political legitimacy, was at the cost of losing its technical depth and capability to actually talk to the actual policy actions needed. The Bureau was even perceived to have failed to capitalize on the momentum created by the success of the 48th Conference, as the follow-up process under the IBE’s responsibility was seen as not meeting the necessary level of quality (UNESCO, 2013).

The bid for heightened political legitimacy of the IBE, a corollary of UNESCO’s own struggles, as the organization was seeing its legitimacy rapidly decreasing in the 90s (Edwards, Jr. et al., 2018; Menashy & Manion, 2016; Mundy, 1999), meant that IBE’s role, and together with it that of the Conference, had to fit UNESCO broader structure, a space that had already become very crowded and where other institutions, such as the Education for All Global Monitoring Report, were already occupying some of the most visible and politically rewarding areas, aligned with the emerging yet dominant new form of global governance of education anchored in the international education agenda. IBE’s loss of legitimacy, *vis-à-vis* the global governance architecture would become cemented in 2015, when the Incheon Framework for Action (UNESCO, 2015), led by UNESCO, insisted on the centrality of the curriculum yet did not allocate to the IBE any explicit

⁶ Author’s translation from original (« Les résolutions de notre Conférence seront bien plutôt un catalogue des solutions possibles. » BIE, 1934, p. 30)

role, while other UNESCO institutions, namely the GEM Report and the UNESCO Institute for Statistics, found their way into the final declaration endorsed by the global education community.

Conclusion: Education is a Political Issue, Justice and Fairness in Education even more

In reference to events that took place in 1964 and led to the premature termination of the ICPE, Hofstetter and Schneuwly titled a chapter of their impressive volume on the history of the International Bureau of Education, “Education is a Political Issue” (Hofstetter & Schneuwly, 2024). This paper in many ways confirms the difficulty of engaging with educational sciences in a neutral, scientific, and independent way at the global level. The initial aspiration of IBE’s founders.

What is shown here is that the current international account of justice and fairness in education, inclusion and equity has inherited several of features from the early years of intergovernmental cooperation in education, as reflected in the final outcomes of the Conference. The focus on and identification of vulnerable groups dates to the very first conferences, starting with women, rural areas, children with disabilities, and was progressively enriched with more categories over the years. Even if the rationale moved from educability and societal usefulness to individuals’ right to education, it remains that those instances of intergovernmental cooperation in education looked into mechanisms and policy solutions to foster, very early, equal access to education. It is also through these instances that acceptable minimum standards for education were established as global values to pursue. Free and compulsory education, minimum reading, writing, and mathematics competencies, decent buildings and infrastructure, all came out in the early years of the ICPE, out of exchanges between the pedagogical experts that shaped the foundation of educational science today. The prevailing notion of justice was, however, one of absolute justice, and comparison between groups, as done currently, was not the perspective taken by delegates at least until statistical argument could be made. The focus was on the injustice created by the fact that some did not get an education, while today the focus is that some do not get an education, while others do. This focus on absolute justice went hand in hand with a perfect procedural justice approach, whereby resolving the injustice primarily meant addressing the processes to provide

these specific groups with education. This allowed for concrete policy recommendations on all aspects of education, from basic inputs to teacher training to pedagogical approaches.

But what this paper also shows is that the sincere pursuit of justice and fairness in education is a political issue. This, in turn, requires addressing questions of recognition, identity, equality of treatment, and in many instances, to compensate for decades of institutionalized and systemic educational exclusion, a view that is held today by many academics and is dominating the scholarly landscape on justice and fairness in education (Montjouridès, 2022). Both the ICE and the current international education agenda have stopped at the door of this endeavor. And this is perhaps where the fate of the IBE and the Conference had been written. Becoming a legitimate entity on the global stage has a cost, that of letting go of some of your intellectual capability and neutrality to fit the narrative of the times, one that does not go into the politically sensitive issues. This historical trajectory cannot be detached from the institutional changes that the IBE had to face to ensure its survival. But as both the locus of knowledge production and of international education authority have changed, so has faded the former brilliance of the Bureau despite its foundational contributions to foster justice and fairness in education.

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